

Impact of Behavior and Attitude on Organizational Training Effectiveness. A special Case Study of Non- Teaching Staff of Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur.

Author's Details: ⁽¹⁾Faheem -ul-Hussain Dehraj ⁽²⁾Bilawal Ali Dayo ⁽³⁾Professor Dr: Noor Shah Bukhari

⁽³⁾Chairman Department of Public Administration ⁽¹⁾M.PHIL/MS Scholar Department of Business Administration,
Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur, Sindh, Pakistan

⁽²⁾Shah Abdul Latif University Khairpur, Sindh, Pakistan.

Abstract:

Keeping in view the gap between training program and training effectiveness, this research was carried out by using attitude and behavior as an independent variables towards the training effectiveness, data was collected by generating the set of questionnaires from the employees of Shah Abdul latif University, khairpur for measuring the role of above mentioned variables through SPSS 18 and conclude that attitude and behavior are significantly and positively related with training effectiveness but the gap is still too large to be filled by different researchers to high light the same issue.

Keywords: Behavior, Attitude, Training Effectiveness.

Introduction:

In this global rigors competition and fast changing environment, utilization of paramount Human Resource capital, ensure competitive advantage and keep the organizations' competitive survival for over the period. Whereas the training is given the utmost importance in this era, jobs are difficult and changing, therefore training is an alternative to cope with changing environmental challenges. The demand for this service grows, therefore the training basic motive is to increase performance and improve quality work, to a required level through gaining skills and knowledge at each job position in working place, decrease waste, enhance productivity and avail high work force efficiency.

Evaluating the influence of training on work place and its role for organizational outcome is an issue of importance for all sort of organizational management. Due to the complex condition of economic pressure, for this purpose the business leaders are more cost and benefit vexatious about the return on training investment due to prevailing economic downturn, to address such problem, over the period evaluating the training effectiveness has been given much focus.

During the past four decades many researchers and professional have done study on measuring the training effectiveness as well factors affecting the training effectiveness. Kirkpatrick (1976) done eminent work in this area and gave four well known "four level of evaluation model", and used so far in training industry. Many other experts did also work on same field in this contribution and brought changes in available models as well. Olson, (1964) said that "If we want to alter the way people act, we need to change their hearts and minds".

This study effort to quest the impact of attitude, behavior and work environment towards training effectiveness. Since attitude is one's feeling which instigating importance to words gaining knowledge from training, where as behavior refers to the individual actions and support to implement the knowledge in work place gained through training, along with working environment is focused as motivating factor as support from co-workers and management to encourage training and development and provide opportunity to perform, another factor which also attract trainees interest toward training effectiveness is reward system.

Review of literature:

Training effectiveness models

Kirkpatrick (1976) stated that difficult task to measure the training effectiveness, which brings the outcome of training program, he explained some training effectiveness measuring models. The first model of four level method of training effectiveness. Level -1 a reaction criteria, it assesses the attitudinal responses of trainees regarding specific training programme. Level-2 a learning criteria, assessment of training outcome i.e material and knowledge learned and gained through training. Level-4 a behavioral criteria, an assessment of practical implementation of skills and expertise by employees, gained through training programme. level-4 a result criteria that how far employees training have caused the organizational outcome and profitability.

Beach, (1980) reported that “training is an organized procedure by which learn knowledge and/ or skill for a definite purpose”, it makes up of skill and knowledge gap where as successful accomplishment of anticipated result and objectives from the training denote “Training Effectiveness”. According Kalemci, P (2005) by scientific approach to measurement and evaluation, a continuous attainment of training program can be availed. For the organization training accomplishment depends to techniques and methods adopted.

Farooq & Khan, (2011) concluded that organization can enhance performances through training and feedback by extensive broaden the implication of these and through other features of training by which performance process of team can get better and in return yield better employee work effectiveness.

Factors affecting Training Effectiveness

Discussed above review is about factors assessing training effectiveness, here efforts being made to identify that which factors affecting the training effectiveness. (Kamal, 2005) notified that training effectiveness of organization affected by many factors such as uncomfortable departmental environment, absence of support from management, unmanaged departmental climate negatively affect the training. Fischer,(2011) reported that open-mindedness is essential to work both from participants and trainer for successful training.

Haslinda & M.Y, 6(2009)) concluded that absence of top management and peers co-operation , employees attitude and training practice scarcity impact the effectiveness of training, these are essential factors should positively be exercised, which then collectively causes for successful training .Tai,(2006) stated that investment on human resource plays a key role to make successful organization by keeping its employees potential and worthwhile because the purpose and execution of training is a key factor to evaluate the desired consequences as planned otherwise training is costly.

Dr.B.K & kant, (2013) according him many factor devaluing training effectiveness but three factors are considered to be stronger I.e, motivation, attitude and emotional intelligence. Manager encourage employees to be adapted in new skills and abilities, next to assure better training effectiveness by encouraging individuals to practice such skills in workplace, attitude determines the learning importance from the training , while emotional leader ever found to be successful in aspiring the workers .

According Elangovan & Karakowsky, (1999) that training effectiveness is enormously affected by work environment, which presenting directly the training outcomes. Wehrmeyer & Chenoweth, (2006) reported that Individual behavior is also affected by the organizational culture i.e. values, belief and adopted coping techniques, a positive and comfortable environment and culture have a big role in managing consistent organization success.

Tracing out the training needs

To understand the need of training for organizations’ is very much essential to know answer the question either the organizations’ problems, objectives or need served by training. Three steps to evaluating the needs, based on organizational analysis i.e. which organizational goals can be availed by personnel training? Where Training and development in required in the organization? Which things will be faced through training? And by scrutiny i.e. who individual required training and why?

Goldstein & Ford, (2002) his study suggested that organizing the systematic need assessment is a first step to training design and can potentially impact the throughout the training programs where as a systematic needs evaluation, guides and stand as basis for design and development of training program. Systematic needs identify the t training needs, job necessities and sort of training to be delivered, can outcome in more effective training.

Longitudinal training effectiveness addresses the post training questions such as, can behavior be persistent overtime? How can training indicate for organization objectives and profitability accomplishments after training? (Nurhazani & Issam, Work Environmental Factors Influncing In Achieving Training Effectiveness In Akaba Special Economic Zone Authority ASEZA, 2012).

Training and job satisfaction

Cascio & Beadwell, (1998) identified that “training , development and concentrated efforts” purpose to improve core-competence, organizational performance, construct and sustain competitive advantages, emphasizing to this, certainly personnel competency is specific knowledge and skills that often upgraded by continuous training and development in supporting to bridge the gap between skills and new knowledge .The organizations needs to assess the level of the employees knowledge, expertise and strength for better performance to their positions, whereas employee’s lower level of expertise caused to their gap of skill (carr, 1999). Figure bellow showing the how best training redress the existing skill gap and enhance job performance.

(Garret & H.K, 2007)

Training is considered vital and related to skills required by the management of an organization that must be retained by the members of an organization to enhance the profitability of accomplishments of its goals. Training assists employees to redress their fear and frustration by work demand to which they are not acquainted in absence expertise to handle efficiently (Chen, Chang, & Yeh, 2004).

Research model:

Hypothesis:

- H1: Attitude is positively related with Training effectiveness (TE).
- H2: Behavior is positively related with Training effectiveness (TE).

Methodology:

Primary data: Data was collected through first hand (Primary source of information) by generating the set of questions in English language consist of three factors of variables using five point measuring scale (strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree).

Secondary data: Data was also used for review of literature and justifying our research work, in this light different researcher papers of various authors were used.

Sampling: Random sampling method was used by collecting the data from the respondents of Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur, especially those respondents were selected who got training.

Statistically methods: In starting, we check the reliability of the instrument by using spss18 through Cronbach's alpha, followed by analysis, we used confirmatory analysis for following three variables.

- 1: Attitude.
- 2: Behavior
- 3: Training Effectiveness.

Diagnostic test: $TE = \alpha + A1 \beta_1 + B2 \beta_2 + \mu$
TE = Training effectiveness (Dependent variable)
A= Attitude (independent variable)
B= Behavior (independent variable)

Results & Discussions:

Reliability analysis:

Attitude:	
Q1: Can work place of your organization be better through training?	
Q2: Have your organization ever organized training?	
Q3: Are you satisfied with your organization training program?	
Q4: Do you believe training have influence on work performance?	
Q5: Are employees of your organization encouraged to strive for continuously to improve performance by training?	
Q6: In your workgroup, steps are taken to deal with poor performers who cannot or will not improve.	
α	= .677
Behavior:	
Q1: In your org: a person influence is based on his ability.	
Q2: Are the opportunities provided to each employee to use his/her skills?	
Q3: Is your work performance evaluated during the period?	
Q4: Behavior of employees in your org: is positive.	
Q5: In your org: rewards are based on performance effectiveness.	
Q6: How over all are you satisfied from your work group?	
α	= .716
Training effectiveness:	
Q1: Trainers had an excellent knowledge of the subject content.	
Q2: I usually had a clear idea of what was expected of me to gain from training.	
Q3: I was given enough material to keep up my interest.	
Q4: I learned to work with people.	
Q5: I learned to plan and manage my work.	
Q6: I feel change in my work after getting training.	
α	= .657
Total α	= .783

Regression Analysis:

$$TE = \alpha + A1 \beta_1 + B2 \beta_2 + \mu$$

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std: Error of the Estimate.
1	.540 ^a	.291	.278	.84955993

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Behavior, Attitude
- b. Dependent Variable: Training Effectiveness.

Adjusted R square is a measure to show over all fitness of the model and in this case the value of adjusted R square is **.278** which states that this model is approximately 28% fit, which further explain that both independent variables namely attitude and behavior is contributing only 28% towards training effectiveness, where as remaining 72% is error term.

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	32.051	2	16.025	22.203	.000 ^a
	Residual	77.949	108	.722		
	Total	110.000	110			

- a. Predictors: (Constant), Behavior, Attitude
- b. Dependent Variable: Training Effectiveness

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-7.559E-17	.081		.000	1.000
	Attitude	.344	.082	.344	4.197	.000
	Behavior	.365	.082	.365	4.452	.000

- a. Dependent Variable: Training Effectiveness

According to the results mentioned in the above table attitude is positively related with training effectiveness but the strength of relationship between attitude and training effectiveness is not too much strong but the significant behavior is also positively related with training effectiveness but the case is same as with the attitude.

Conclusion:

Training effectiveness is debatable and burning issue of different organizations , which are focusing on training and development, it is not necessary that if training program is initiated it will be successful but the effectiveness of that program matters, in this perspective attitude and behavior of employees is directly related with training effectiveness

Limitations & recommendations:

This research is restricted at the premises of Shah Abdul Latif University, Khaipur, during the time of depress budgetary conditions. Whereas its results may vary over time as per budgetary condition. This research contributes only 28% based on two variables Attitude and behavior towards the training effectiveness, whereas remaining 72% is needed further to be explored by the researchers.

Bibliography

- Alfaro, L., Chanda, A., Ozcan, S., & Sayek, S. (2004). FDI and Economic Growth: The Role of Local Financial Markets. *Journal of International Economic* , 64, 113-134.
- Amsden, L. (1989). *Asia's Next Giant: South Korea and Late Industrialisation*. New York: Oxford University Press .
- Arize, A. C. (1996, 1998). The Effect of Exchange Rate Uncertainty on Export Growth Evidence from Korean Data. *International Economic Journal* , 10 (3), 49-60.
- Balassa, B. (1978). exports and Economic Growth; Further Evidence. *Journal of Economic Development* , 05, 181-189.
- Beach, D. S. (1980). *"Personal-The Management of People at Work"*. New York: MacMillan Publishing Company, pp.244.
- Broll, U., & Eckwert, B. (1999). Exchange Rate Volatility and International Trade. *Southern Economic Journal* , 66:1, 178-185.
- carr, W. F. (1999, December). Designing An Effective Training Evaluation Process.
- Cascio, W., & Beadwell. (1998). *Applied Psychology in Human Resources Management*, Upper Saddle River, N.J: Prentice- Hall.
- Chaudhary, & Qaisrani. (2002). Trade Instability, Investment and Economic Growth in Pakistan. *Pakistan Economic and Social Review* , XL, NO. 1 (Summer), pp 57-73.
- Chen, T., Chang, P., & Yeh, C. (2004). "A study of career needs, career development programs, job satisfaction and the turnover intensity of R & D personnel". *Career Development International* , vol.9, No.4, 424-37.
- Dr. B.K, P., & Kant, S. (2013). A Review of Factors Affecting Training Effectiveness Vis-A-Vis Managerial Implication and Future Research Directions. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences* , 2-1, 151-164.
- Edwards, S. (1987). Real Exchange Rate Variability: An Empirical Analysis of the Developing Countries Case. *International Economic Journal* , 1:1, 91-106.
- Elangovan, A., & Karakowsky, I. (1999). The role of Trainee and environmental Factor in Transfers of Training. *An exploratory Frame work, Leadership & Organization Development Journal* , 20(5), 268-276.
- Farooq, M., & Khan, D. A. (2011). Impact of Training and Feedback on Employee Performance. *Far East Journal of Psychology and Business* , vol.5. No.1.
- Fischer, R. (2011). 'Cross-Cultural Training Effects on cultural Essentialism Belief and Cultural Intelligence". *International Journal of Intercultural Relations* , 35(6), 767-775.
- Garret, J., & H.K, B. (2007). How to measure Management Training and Development Effectiveness. *Journal of European Industrial Training*. vol.14. 9., pp Download 2-12-2012.
- Goldstein, I., & Ford, J. (2002). *Training in organizations Needs assessment, development, and evaluation* (4th, Belmont, CA: wadsworth ed.).
- Grossman, G., & Helpman, E. (1991). *Innovation and Growth in Global Economy*. Cambridge, The MIT Press .
- Haslinda, A., & M.Y, M. (2009). "The Effectiveness Of Training in the Public service". *American Journal of scientific Resrach* , 39-51.

Kalemci,P. (2005). "General overview of Training Effectiveness and Measurement Models". *Journal of commerce and Tourism Education Faculty,1 (2005)*, 144-156.

Kamal, S. B. (2005). "No idea?Evaluating the Effectiveness of Creativity Training",. *Journal of European industrial Training* , 29(2), 102-111.

kirkpatrick, D. (1976). *Evaluation of Training, Training and development hand book: A guide to human resource management*. New york: McGraw Hill-company.

Nurhazani, M. S., & Issam, M. A.-M. (2012). Work Environmental Factors Influencing In Achieving Training Effectiveness In Akaba Special Economic Zone Authority ASEZA. *A Academic Reasearch International* , 2, No3., pp 10.

Olson, J. T. (1964). *Do Attitude Determine Behavior?* Ralph Waldo Emerson.

Tai, W. T. (2006). Effect of Training framing,General Self- Efficacy and Training Motivation on Trainees' training Effectiveness,Personnel Review. 35(1),pp.213-224.

Wehrmeyer, w., & Chenoweth, J. (2006). The Role and Effectiveness of Coconsulting Education Training Courses Offered by Higher Education Institutions in Further the Implementation of Sustainable Development. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education* , 7(2), 129-141.